

CO₂ REDUCTION VIA CARBONATE LOOPING – A NOVEL CARBON CAPTURE TECHNOLOGY

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CARBON CAPTURE AND STORAGE

- Coal fired power plants account for 40% of worldwide CO₂ emissions. [1]
- Shifting to CO₂ free power production (hydro, solar, wind, biomass, etc.) will take many decades.
- Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) is regarded the only probable short-term CO₂ mitigation option for coal fired power plants (current price: 30-70 \$/tCO₂). [1]
- The largest cost component of CCS is the capture of CO₂ from flue gases prior to transportation and storage. [1]
- Carbonate Looping is a carbon capture technology which is significantly cheaper than current options (MEA, oxyfuel)

Figure 1. Illustration of the Carbon Capture and Storage Concept. Fossil fuel is extracted and combusted at a power plant for electricity production. Instead of emitting the CO₂ produced by combustion to the atmosphere, it is compressed and transported to suitable storage locations deep under ground or under water. The Carbonate Looping process is a CO₂ capture technology (point 2 in the figure), i.e. a process in which dilute CO₂ from a power plant flue gas is concentrated before compression, transportation and sequestration. Figure adapted from [2].

THE CARBONATE LOOPING PROCESS

- Captures CO₂ by reaction with CaO. CO₂ released again by heating:
 $\text{CaO} + \text{CO}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{CaCO}_3 \quad \Delta H_r = -178 \text{ kJ/mol}$
- Produces additional electricity.
- Uses cheap limestone as sorbent that can be re-used in the cement industry to provide significant CO₂ bonuses.
- Simultaneously captures SO₂ from the flue gas, making expensive flue gas desulfurization units unnecessary.

Figure 2. Flowsheet illustrating the Carbonate Looping process. A CO₂-rich flue gas reacts with CaO to form CaCO₃ (carbonation) while the remaining flue gas components are purged. The CaCO₃ is then heated to release the CO₂ as a pure gas stream (calcination), simultaneously regenerating the CaO and enabling the loop to start over. The CO₂ carrying capacity of CaO decreases for each completed loop but the spent CaO can be used for almost CO₂ free cement production.

REALISTIC CARBONATE LOOPING EXPERIMENTS REQUIRE AN EXTRAORDINARY PIECE OF EQUIPMENT

- The CO₂ carrying capacity of a CaO particle decreases with the number of calcination-carbonation cycles, N:
$$\text{CO}_2 \text{ Carrying Capacity}(N) = \frac{\text{moles of CO}_2 \text{ captured in cycle } N}{\text{moles of CaO in particle}} \cdot 100\%$$
- The CO₂ carrying capacity is crucial to the overall Carbonate Looping process. It can be determined using thermogravimetric analysis (TGA, Figure 3). However, TGA's typically heat and cool at <20 K/min and since CO₂-CaO equilibrium considerations (Figure 4) require that the temperature must be above 900°C during calcination and below 700°C during carbonation, experiments at realistic conditions are seldom performed.
- To emulate a real Carbonate Looping process, a TGA capable of heating at an amazing 1000 K/min has been acquired. Figure 5 shows the great importance of operating at realistic conditions.

Figure 3. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). Sample mass is measured while temperature and surrounding gas composition can be changed. As one mole of CaO weighs 44% less than one mole of CaCO₃, TGA is suited for investigating the calcination and carbonation reactions.

Figure 4. Equilibrium partial pressure of CO₂ over CaO vs. temperature. Calcination requires the equilibrium CO₂ pressure to be above 1 bar while it needs to be below 0.01-0.02 bar during carbonation to obtain good capture efficiency.

Figure 5. CO₂ carrying capacity vs. the number of calcination-recarbonation cycles the particles have experienced. The more realistic the calcination conditions, the faster the decay in carrying capacity. The small figure shows a typical calcination-carbonation cycle. Carbonation at 650°C in 15% CO₂.

REFERENCES

- [1] IPCC, *IPCC Special Report on Carbon Dioxide Capture and Storage*, (2005)
[2] www.geos.ed.ac.uk/ccsresources, Scottish Centre for Carbon Storage, School of GeoSciences, University of Edinburgh (retrieved 10/06-2010)
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CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The Carbonate Looping process is a promising technology for drastically lowering CO₂ emissions via Carbon Capture and Storage. An experimental setup that allows unique experiments on Carbonate Looping is running continuously and many interesting results have already been obtained, leaving great promise for future results.